

Human Capital Perspective of Previous Industrial Revolutions: Review in Support of 4IR and its Possible Impacts

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Abstract

Globally, the industrial revolution is a concept used to capture the different periods that heralds major changes in the society due to technological advancements. Previously, there existed only three industrial revolutions however; in recent times, the possible impacts of fourth industrial revolution (4IR) through its technologies have been the centre of attention in many discussions. While some scholars raise arguments in support of the 4IR saying it will have a far-reaching impact across industries globally, others simply view it as a soon-fading fad. Sequel to the dichotomy, this study from the human capital perspective reviews the previous phases of industrial revolutions to build an argument in support of the 4IR and its possible impacts. The review reveals that as different technologies emerged in the previous phases of the industrial revolution, the nature of work, workplace and ultimately; skill-needs in those revolutions changed. Therefore, this study argues that the 4IR is indeed a revolution looking at the distinctive elements of the 4IR and the probable impacts of these 4IR elements.

Introduction

Industrial revolution is a ubiquitous term used by historians in describing phases of technological shifts with an influence that has greatly affected the society (Klingenberg and Antunes Jr, 2017). Scholars such as Kagermann, Wahlster, and Helbig (2013) and Stearns (2018) otherwise refer to industrial revolution as industrialization. According to Stearns (2018), industrialization has the highest significance in terms of advancement in the history of man in the last 300 years as its effects on both the old and modern societies keep unfolding and require constant readjustment. The advanced nature of the present-day technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Augmented Reality, Drones, and Internet of Things (IoT) are causing drastic changes globally. In view of this, Schwab (2015) posits that another drastic alteration to human history is looming which could lead to another industrial revolution. Thus, professionals and academics across local and international platforms are discussing the dimensions that the 4IR might take and its probable impacts on the global society in general and the workforce in particular.

Scholars such as Brynjolfsson, McAfee, and Spence (2014), Fullan (2016) and Magwentshu, Rajagopaul, Chui and Singh (2019) propose that from a human capital point of view, the 4IR will require a new level of skills and skills-set in the fast-changing workplace. Nevertheless, Scholars such as Rifkin (2011) and Cetrulo and Nuvolari (2019) contend that the 4IR is simply hype. Thus, there seem to be a contention in discussions around the 4IR and its probable impacts. Hence, this study from a human capital perspective reviews the previous phases of industrial revolutions to build an argument in support of the 4IR and its possible impacts. According to Becker (2009), human capital refers to the skills, competencies, and knowledge possessed by a worker which determines their value to the organization. Therefore, the subsequent sections of this study details the three previous industrial revolutions in relation to the nature of work, workplace and skill-needs prevalent in those revolutions, the distinctive elements of the 4IR and the possible 4IR skill-needs.

Previous Phases of the Industrial Revolution: A Human Capital Perspective

Studies on one hand reveal that series of industrial revolutions have occurred over the last 200 years (Klingenberg and Antunes Jr, 2017; as well as Liao, Loures, Deschamps, Brezinski, and Venâncio, 2017), or 250 years (Stearns, 2018). Thus, the exact aggregate and time lag of each industrial revolution remains unclear (Klingenberg and Antunes Jr, 2017). On the other hand, Scholars such as Kagermann et al. (2013); Klingenberg and Antunes Jr (2017); and Liao et al. (2017) highlighted four phases of the industrial revolution from the purview of evolving technology. Hence, this section beginning with the pre-industrialization era chronicles the three previous industrial revolutions in relation to the nature of work, workplace and skill-needs prevalent in those revolutions.

Pre-Industrialization Era

Prior to the 18th Century, 'work' existed in crude form as it only involves a set of informally transferred methods and skills that are largely agrarian and artisanal. This implies that production was in distinctive little quantities and the economy was largely monopolistic as a high level of skill was required in the prevalent work environment. Bayraktar, and Ataç (2018) comment that before the industrial revolution, the economy was largely driven through cultivation, livestock farming, trading and craftsmanship hence, being energetic was an advantage. Egbetokun, Yun, Zhao, and Kim (2018) trace the era preceding the industrial revolutions to 10,000 years ago and captions it as 'the agrarian revolution' wherein livestock were domesticated, and novel agricultural technologies were introduced, bringing about enhanced production of food, sizeable increase in the populace and increase in fixed settlement. This implies that work was specialized in the pre-industrialization era a result, high level of skill consisting of artisanal and/or agricultural skills-set was required making workshops and farms prominent as workplaces.

The First Industrial Revolution

Literatures such as Xu et al (2018) and Kagermann, et al (2013) show that there are disparities with regards to the exact year that the first industrial revolution began. For instance, Xu et al (2018) reports that it started in 1760, Stearns (2018) declared that it began in the 1770s, *Klingenberg and Antunes Jr* (2017) stated that it started in 1784 while Kagermann, et al (2013); and Liao et al (2017) simply stated that it took-off at the end of the 18th century. However, the trend in the writings show that these researchers agree that it kicked off at the end of the 18th century. Suffice to state that the first industrial revolution commenced sometimes towards the end of the 18th century.

Furthermore, Scholars such as *Klingenberg and Antunes Jr* (2017) and Stearns (2018) unanimously stated that Britain played host to the first Industrial Revolution. In the First Industrial Revolution, production was mechanized using water and steam power (Kagermann et al 2013; Schwab, 2015; *Klingenberg and Antunes Jr*, 2017; and Liao et al 2017; Xu, David, and Kim, 2018; Stearns, 2018, Uleanya and Yu, 2019). Animal and human efforts were replaced with water or coal or steam power (*Klingenberg and Antunes Jr*, 2017) and machinery such as mechanical loom (Kagermann, et al 2013). Xu et al (2018) expounded that through the steam engine, a society that was predominantly agricultural and primitive transited to a new manufacturing process wherein coal was used as the major source of energy while trains became the major channel for conveyance.

This development caused an unprecedented increase in various sectors (*Klingenberg and Antunes Jr*, 2017) with the textile and steel industries prevailing as regards recruitment, worth of production and capital invested (Xu et al, 2018). Furthermore, the development transcended England to France and then to Germany (Ladenburg, 2007) as well as other parts of the Western Europe and the new United States (Stearns, 2018). In addition, a working-class emerged; work and private life was segregated and the urban areas grew (Hobsbawm, 2016). Thus, drastic modifications occurred in economic and social life (*Klingenberg and Antunes Jr*, 2017).

Klingenberg and Antunes Jr (2017) highlight that the demographic trend in the first industrial revolution era had a dual effect on the economy as demand was created and labour supply was amplified. Karanikola and Panagiotopoulos (2018) argue that the first industrial revolution has a paradoxical impact in that it is connected to the advancement of the capitalist system on the one hand and it triggered major structural alterations socially, economically and culturally on the other. Gera and Singh (2019) assert that the impact of the first industrial revolution is double-sided as mechanization assisted the capitalist to counter workers' associations and yet bestowed unprecedented power on the workers.

Several jobs were created for many with low level of skills (Gera and Singh, 2019), because neither intense scientific knowledge nor huge sums of money were required from the workers (*Klingenberg and Antunes Jr*, 2017). However, the workforce had to adapt to an unfamiliar work context that is stringent, draining and repetitive as well as entails a high level of restraint and education (Karanikola and Panagiotopoulos, 2018). This led to the emergence of a working-class whose only means of livelihood was their wages (Hobsbawm, 2016). This means that the dynamics of work radically changed from specialized to generalized as production was mechanized using the water and steam power technology. Consequently, the high-level skill need in the pre-industrialization era was no longer needed in the first industrial revolution in that low level of skill specifically operation and control of machines was needed. Thus, the factory became the most prominent workplace.

The Second Industrial Revolution

Studies such as *Klingenberg and Antunes Jr*, 2017, Stearns, 2018 as well as Uleanya and Yu, 2019 reveal inconsistencies with regards to the actual year wherein the second industrial revolution commenced. For instance, *Klingenberg and Antunes Jr* (2017) as well as Uleanya and Yu (2019) opine that it began in 1870, Stearns (2018) stated that its beginning is traceable to the 1880s, Xu et al (2018) deviated stating that it started in 1900 while Kagermann, et al (2013); and Liao et al (2017) chronicles early 20th century as its beginning. Nonetheless, most of these Academics consent to the commencement of the second industrial revolution commencing sometimes around the late 19th century to early 20th century. Suffice to state therefore, that the late

19th century to the early 20th century captures the second industrial revolution. Klingenberg and Antunes Jr (2017) allude that the United States spear-headed this revolution. However, Stearns (2018) expatiates that Russia, Japan, Canada, Australia, and certain parts of eastern and southern Europe, concurrently hosted this revolution on their shores. The second industrial revolution was marked by mass production through electric power (Kagermann et al 2013; Schwab, 2015; *Klingenberg and Antunes Jr*, 2017; Liao et al 2017; Stearns, 2018; and Xu et al 2018).

This advancement led to an increase in the total factories (Hobsbawm, 2016) as productivity increased in several industries like railroads, steel and chemical (Klingenberg and Antunes Jr., 2017; Uleanya and Yu, 2019). According to Xu et al (2018), the advent of the internal combustion engine occasioned a period of swift industrial development by means of mass production powered by oil and electricity. The foregoing reveals that the enhancement of the transport industry fast-tracked urbanization in that the working class easily and increasingly migrated to the erstwhile small settlements that were transformed into industrial hubs by means of the railroads and automobile cars.

Furthermore, there was a notable growth in income, accessibility to long-lasting consumer goods, and the standards of living (Frieden, 2008). Hence, organisations grew significantly such that some had more influence than their governments (Klingenberg and Antunes Jr, 2017). Conversely, although, the massive production amplified the quantity of produce through the usage of specialized machineries, however, the machineries were costly. Klingenberg and Antunes Jr (2017) in their view opine that although mass production of identical products resulted in reduced prices and allowed for more demand, the process of production turned out to be extremely inflexible such that a slight difference in the product takes a lot of time and money. In view of the stereotyped production process, the nature of work was no longer complicated resulting in a further low level skill need.

Scholastic discussions vis-à-vis the impact of mass production of the second industrial revolution on the workforce show that the nature of work and skill changed favourably as more jobs were created and the workers emancipated to the point that they influenced the work policies and conditions. Frieden (2008) avers that mass production in the second industrial revolution stimulated the necessity for unskilled workers to the extent that certain nations provided benefits in order to attract workers from overseas. Karanikola and Panagiotopoulos (2018) add that the second industrial revolution afforded the working-class independence and sufficient capacity needed in requesting for improved working contexts from their employers. Gera and Singh (2019) explain that mass production assisted in the deskilling of labour by stripping artisans of their duties which are complicated and reassigning such duties amongst numerous workers in a cost-effective way, thereby, creating more jobs and boosting the demand for products as well as services. In essence, work in the second industrial revolution was further generalized leading to an increase in the demand for low level of skill especially operation and control of machines. Thus, the factory as a workplace gained more prominence.

The Third Industrial Revolution

The exact year wherein the third industrial revolution occurred cannot be accounted for as there are discrepancies in the archives in this regard. Xu et al (2018) reports that it started in 1960, *Klingenberg and Antunes Jr* (2017) declared that it began in 1969, Stearns (2018) stated that its beginning is traceable to the 1960s, Kagermann, et al (2013) state that it took-off in the early 1970s, and Liao et al (2017) chronicles mid 1970s as its starting point. Nevertheless, it suffices to note that most of these Scholars agree on 1960s-1970s therefore, we can safely conclude that the third industrial revolution spans through the mid-20th century to early 21st century. *Klingenberg and Antunes Jr* (2017) archives that the United States led this revolution.

Stearns (2018) argues that this revolution was led by the Pacific Rim and 200years later, it spread out to Turkey, India, Brazil and some other segments of Latin America. The demographic changes, technology-related developments in communications, and fierce competition brought about by the second industrial revolution forced organisations, governments and educational institutions to invest heavily in research and development. This huge investment in research and development from these trio occasioned the automation of production through information and communications technology. Therefore, the Third Industrial Revolution was marked by automated production by means of electronics and information technology (Kagermann et al 2013; Schwab, 2015; Klingenberg, and Antunes Jr, 2017; Liao et al 2017; Stearns, 2018; Xu et al 2018; and Uleanya and Yu, 2019).

The Third Industrial Revolution became notable for its automation of production using electronics and information technology in factories (Liao et al, 2017) instead of screwing or welding sub-parts with each other (Xu et al, 2018). Consequently, most tasks previously executed manually and some of the mental works were predominantly executed with machines (Kagermann, et al 2013). Hence, series of technologies called Advanced Manufacturing Technologies (AMT) which inter alia includes Computer Integrated Manufacturing (CIM), Computer-Aided Design (CAD), Computer-Aided Manufacturing (CAM), and Flexible Manufacturing Systems (FMS) was birthed (*Klingenberg and Antunes Jr*, 2017). Although, this pattern implies that there was progress, nonetheless, the third industrial revolution delivered below anticipation (*Klingenberg and Antunes Jr*, 2017)

owing to deficiencies of skilled specialists, high costs of software and the necessity of capital outlay in contemporary equipment (Freeman and Soete, 2008).

Although, through this revolution, production became more flexible, faster, accurate and customized, however, the situations surrounding the economy in this period slowed down the pace of this revolution. Organisations had to develop a survival strategy in the midst of the harsh economic condition hence, in order to cut cost, many moved their production hubs from the industrial areas to the non-industrial areas where labour was abundant and very cheap. This cost-saving mechanism slowed down this revolution in that abundant and cheap labour lacked the requisite skill and the environment itself was deficient of the needed infrastructure. Thus, occasionally, organisations had to outsource from the industrialized areas to bridge the gaps.

Freeman and Soete (2008) declared that scarcity of skilled experts, increasing costs of software and the necessity for huge funding of new machineries among other factors decelerated the pace of the spread of technologies linked to computing. Findings from International Telecommunication Union (2015) reveal that regardless of the explosive use of the internet by 3.2 billion people globally, only 7% of family units in the developing nations have internet accessibility. Klingenberg and Antunes Jr (2017) juxtaposed the double-edged impact of this revolution stating that though, globalization strengthened the Information Technology application owing to the communication needs and reduced labour costs, nevertheless, outdated connections, shortage of knowledge, and organisational restrictions amongst other challenges connected to execution heightened the expenses.

Karanikola and Panagiotopoulos (2018) noted that in the third industrial revolution, workers required a high level of technical knowledge therefore, the evolution and spreading of digital skills became a significant area of reference for sundry domestic and global educational and workers' training policies. Gera and Singh (2019) observed that the attention of capitalists moved from low-skilled workers to medium skilled workers because productivity increased with computers than existing machines, consequently, workers who possessed the required skills replaced the low-skilled workers especially in the manufacturing sector. Hence, Gera and Singh (2019) conclude that jobs were not eroded, rather, the nature of employment changed radically as the nature of skill-need changed, thereby, restoring the necessity of skills in the work environment and assisting the computer and service industries to thrive more than their manufacturing counterparts. Consequent on the afore-explained, it is clear that the nature of work in the third industrial revolution became highly technical: shifting the skill emphasis from low to a medium level as operation of computer became largely required. Thus, the office became the most prominent workplace.

Shown in Table 1 below is a summary of the trends in the workforce and skills of the previous industrial revolutions as afore-discussed.

Table 1: Workforce and skills trend of the previous industrial revolutions

S/N	Phase of IR	Period	Prominent Industry (ies)	Nature of Work	Workplace	Skill(s)-Need
1.	Pre-IR	Before 18 th Century	Craft and Farming	Specialized	Workshop and Farm	High level of artisanal and/or agricultural skill
2.	IR	18th century to Mid-19th century	Manufacturing- Textile, Steel and Transport	Generalized	Factory	Low level of skill-Operation and control of machines
3.	2nd IR	Late 19th century to Early 20th century	Manufacturing- Transport, Steel and Oil	Generalized	Factory	Low level of skill-Operation and control of machines
4.	3rd IR	Mid-20th century to Early 21th century	Services- ICT and Electronics	Technical	Office	Medium level of skill- Operation of computer

Note: IR means Industrial Revolution and ICT means Information Communications Technology

Source: Researchers' view emanating from reviewed literatures

Sequel to the three industrial revolutions reviewed above, it can be inferred that the emergence of unique technological innovation in a bid to solve rising needs in each of these previous revolutions have led to changing dynamics in the nature of work and workplace in those eras. These changing dynamics affected the level of skills and skills-set that is needed per time in these previous revolutions. It is therefore critical to explore the ongoing changes in the nature of work and workplace in recent times and the probable impact that such changes could have on the skills needed. Hence, in the next section, this study details the changing nature of work and

workplace using the distinctive elements of the 4IR therefore, arguing that the 4IR is indeed a revolution. Subsequently, the study captures the probable impacts that such changes could have on the skills needed.

Distinctive Elements of the 4IR

Notwithstanding the several discussions on 4IR that is ongoing all over the world, within different countries and across many industries, some Scholars such as Priscearu (2016), and Lee et al (2018) have affirmed divergent opinions as regards whether these new developments represent a new revolution. Priscearu (2016) observes that authors have varying views as to whether this revolution is indeed the 4IR. Lee et al (2018) affirms that the 4IR is marked by several arguments; however, the beginning of these arguments is whether there is indeed a 4IR. Rifkin (2011) considers the changes that are being caused by the current convergence of communication and energy as the actual beginning of the third industrial revolution. Cetrulo and Nuvolari (2019) opine that notwithstanding the enormous concentration given to the industry 4.0 currently, it is not a disruptive alteration rather, it is hype.

Schwab (2015) argues that irrespective of the varying meanings and scholarly contentions as regards the industrial revolutions, there is indeed another industrial revolution that is building on the third industrial revolution. Furthermore, Schwab (2015) contends that the 4IR essentially differs from the preceding revolutions because the manner in which technologies are merging and their interplay transverse physical, digital and biological spheres. In addition to the increased speed in industrial processes through rapidly changing technologies, Kagermann et al (2013), Brettel, Friederichsen, Keller and Rosenberg (2014), Deloitte (2014) as well as *Klingenberg and Antunes Jr* (2017) agree that the 4IR differs from the different industrial revolutions on the basis of horizontal integration as a result of value networks, digital integration of engineering throughout the full value chain, vertical integration and networking of production systems. Figure 1 below illustrates the elements that distinguish the 4IR from the previous industrial revolutions.

Figure 1: Distinctive Elements of the Fourth Industrial Revolution

Source: Deloitte (2014). "Industry 4.0: Challenges and solutions for the digital transformation and use of exponential technologies"

The foregoing denotes that there is an ongoing transformation by recent technologies that allows for smart production systems, unprecedented global chain networks and digital integration of engineering across the entire value chain. Therefore, vertical networking is aided because of the smart production systems that are currently in existence as opposed to the automated production systems of the third industrial revolution. This implies that organizations can regulate, guide, and protect its contractors, wholesalers and trading sites thereby maintaining the organization's value in the supply chain. Consequently, the processes of the organization are well managed

at a reduced cost leading to an improved efficiency and ultimately increasing customer satisfaction. The recent technologies have also enabled new global chain networks thereby aiding horizontal integration. This means that organizations occupying similar stages in the supply chain can collaborate thereby increasing their share of the market at a reduced cost. In addition, these recent technologies provide a basis for digitalized networking of value chain engineering. This indicates that the recent technologies provides a digital platform via which organizations can blend the processes involved in adding value to their raw materials in the production of finished goods thereby increasing their competitive advantage in the industry. It suffices from these distinguishing elements of the 4IR to state that currently, there is an accelerated change in the nature of work from technical in the third industrial revolution to digital therefore, the workplace is increasingly automated. The fact that there is a change in the nature of work and workplace provides sufficient argument that the 4IR is indeed a revolution. Considering that change in the nature of work and workplace leads to changes in the level of skill and skills-set needed per time, the next section presents the possible impacts that the ongoing changes could have on the skills needed.

Probable Impacts of the 4IR on Skill-Needs

Future of Jobs Report (2016) observes that the increasing rate of radical changes in relation to technology, demography and socio-economy is causing transformation in businesses and their frameworks thus, disrupting the skills-set that employers require and limiting the lifespan of existing skills in professions that are vulnerable to technological changes and the non-vulnerable ones. Consequently, Future of Jobs Report (2016) submits that in every industry, location and work-group, the ability to comprehend the existing skills-set and almost instantaneously as well as precisely predict, expect and get ready for prospective work features and skills-needs will be progressively necessary for organisations, marketplace regulators, civil societies and everyone to thrive. In other words, these submissions from Future of Jobs Report (2016) show that to have an edge in the fast-changing work environment of the 4IR, stakeholders will require an accurate forecast of the skills that will be needed in view of the changes in the nature of work.

World Economic Forum carried out a future of jobs survey in 2016 with specific focus on 35 practical skills and capabilities which are largely utilised from one industry and job family to another. Figure 2 below contains the 35 core work-related skills in their various groupings namely: abilities, basic skills and cross functional skills.

Figure 2: Core Work-Related Skills

Source: Future of Jobs Report (2016). 'Employment, skills and workforce strategy for the fourth industrial revolution.'

Findings from the future of jobs survey by WEF in the Future of Jobs Report (2016) reveals the following underlisted:

- By 2020, not less than one third of the skill sets that will be considered essential in a number of professions will include skills that are currently considered trivial.

- Within the span of 2015 to 2020, the Media, Entertainment and Information industry is anticipated to have the highest level of skills stability whereas the Financial Services & Investors industry is anticipated to have the highest level of skills disruption.
- In relation to the overall level of demand for different skills by 2020, 36% of every work across every industry is likely to view complex problem-solving as an essential skill, while 4% is likely to view physical abilities as an essential skill.
- Generally, from one industry to another, social skills like persuasiveness, emotional intelligence and tutoring have a higher likelihood of being demanded than confined technical skills like coding or operating and controlling machineries.
- Content skills like ICT-related knowledge and active learning; cognitive abilities like creativeness as well as mathematical logic; and process skills like active listening and analytic reasoning are expected to increasingly grow as a fraction of essential skills.
- Most profession that strictly requires technical skills will begin to demand for creative and interpersonal skills.
- In summary, many participants in the WEF's future of jobs survey expect that lots of professions will need a high level of cognitive abilities like creativeness, critical thinking and problem solving as a portion of their essential skill-set.

The foregoing findings show that the 4IR entails a shift from medium technical skills needed in the third industrial revolution to a high-level skill needs such as social skills, content skills, cognitive abilities, process skills and creative skills. Fullan (2016) discloses that in the 4IR, the importance of in-depth learning which involves the six Cs namely character, collaboration, citizenship, communication, critical thinking and creativity cannot be ignored. Manda and Backhouse (2017) argue that regardless of the heightened fear that technology will substitute humans, the 4IR will create job openings for which human reasoning and skills would be the most relevant. Brynjolfsson, McAfee, and Spence (2014) as well as Xu, David, and Kim (2018) affirm that creative and innovative individuals will be rare to find because beyond capital, talents will be the major factor of production in the 4IR.

Karanikola and Panagiotopoulos (2018) maintain that there are three levels of skills required in the 21st century namely: fundamental skills such as numerical competence, reading ability and rudimentary digital literacy; core capabilities together with advanced skills such as science and foreign languages; and transversal skills such as entrepreneurial ability, intellection, problem solving, teach-ability, financial intelligence, innovativeness and creativeness is another important category. Passion Incubator (2018) highlights intellectual flexibility, service inclination, negotiation skills, creative thinking, judgment and decision making, people management, emotional aptitude, critical thinking, coordination, and management of risk as the ten topmost soft skills that are currently sought for in a worker. Figure 3 below shows the comparison of the top 10 core skills set at 2015 and what it will likely look like in 2020 as outlined by Future of Jobs Report (2016).

Figure 3: Top 10 Skills in 2015 and Expected Top 10 Skills in 2020

Source: Future of Jobs Report (2016). 'Employment, skills and workforce strategy for the fourth industrial revolution.'

Recently, the World Bank Group published a report titled 'World Development Report', based on a cross-country and cross-industry survey of 'the changing nature of work'. World Development Report (2019) explains that though, the recent technologies are causing the need for low-level skills that are repetitive and work-defined to decrease nevertheless, they have led to an increase in the need for high-level skills such as non-repetitive cognition which includes critical thinking; socio-behaviour which comprises emotional intelligence as well as collaboration; and flexibility in gaining multi-skills as they cannot be automated. For instance, in a particular industry in Vietnam, employees who engaged in non-repetitive systematic duties make 23% higher while employees involved in interactive duties make 13% higher than their counterparts involved in non-systematic, solitary and mechanized duties (World Development Report, 2019).

Furthermore, employees in Armenia and Georgia who are problem solvers and can learn new skills get an extra payment of 20% (World Development Report, 2019). In addition, managers in Benin, Liberia, Malawi, and Zambia agree that aside from technical skills, collaboration, communication, and problem-solving skills have the utmost significance (World Development Report, 2019).

The academic discussions with regards to the probable impacts of the 4IR on skill-needs that has been considered in this section of the study shows that the basic skills, core competencies and cross-functional skills are the three levels of skills that operate in the work environment. In addition, most of the employees currently possess basic skills or at best core competencies and a little fraction possess the cross-functional skills. Figure 4 below is a pyramid summarizing the current state of the skill-groups in the current work environment.

Figure 4: Current State of the Skill-Groups in the Current Work Environment

Source: Researchers' own

Furthermore, studies highlighted above reveal that emphasis has shifted from basic skills to the core competencies and the cross-functional skills most especially. Figure 5 below summarizes the probable skills-needs of the 4IR on the basis of the extent of emphasis placed on them in relevant discussions above.

Figure 5: Skills-Need Emphasis In View Of the Fourth Industrial Revolution

Source: Researchers' own

Conclusion

This study reviewed the previous phases of industrial revolutions providing arguments supporting the 4IR and its possible impacts. The study began with an x-ray of the nature of work, workplace and skill-needs starting from the pre-industrialization era, to the first, second and third industrial revolutions. Findings reveal that as different technologies emerged in the previous phases of the industrial revolution, the nature of work, workplace and ultimately; skill-needs in those revolutions changed. In view of this finding, the study then details the changing nature of work and workplace using the distinctive elements of the 4IR. It is observed that there is an ongoing transformation by recent technologies that allows for smart production systems, unprecedented global chain networks and digital integration of engineering across the entire value chain.

Consequent on these distinguishing elements of the 4IR, it is deduced that there is currently an accelerated change in the nature of work from technical in the third industrial revolution to digital, making the workplace increasingly automated. Therefore, the study argues that the 4IR is indeed a revolution. Following the finding that changes in the nature of work and workplace culminates into change in the level of skill and skills-set needed; the study discussed the possible impacts of the 4IR on skill-needs. This discussion reveals that the 4IR entails a shift from medium technical skills needed in the third industrial revolution to a high-level skillneed. Furthermore, three skills-set namely cross-functional skills, core competencies and basic skills were identified. In addition, the cross-functional skills were the most emphasized 4IR skills-need while the core competencies were identified as essential 4IR skills-need and basic skills recognized as needed but not so emphasized 4IR skills-need.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following is recommended to ensure a beneficial 4IR globally:

- Employers need to invest in human capital development to ascertain that their employees possess the high-level human capital needed for relevance in the 4IR workplace. To start with, the learning and development function in every organization can begin by ensuring that its staff are digitally literate.
- This study was limited to a review however, an empirical study can be conducted using qualitative, quantitative or mixed method.
- Perceptions of major stakeholder in human capital development such as lecturers, students as well as learning and development professionals with regard to the probable 4IR skill-needs can be explored from the context of different nations with emphasis on the African continent.

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